

Load Flow Solution of a Radial Distribution Network

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ABSTRACT

The load flow solution of a radial distribution feeder is crucial for efficient operation and planning of power distribution systems. In radial systems, the power flows in a single direction, from the source to the loads, through a series of distribution lines and transformers. Load flow analysis helps in determining the voltage profile, power losses, and the optimal distribution of real and reactive power throughout the system. The solution methods for load flow in radial distribution networks often involve iterative techniques, such as the Newton-Raphson method or Gauss-Seidel method. This conventional load flow solution method, which was essentially developed to solve problems posed at the transmission network level can encounter convergence problems when applied to distribution network. This paper introduces a method for solving the load flow problem in radial distribution feeders, avoiding conventional methods such as Gauss-Seidel, Newton-Raphson, and fast decoupled methods. The proposed approach uses a forward sweeping technique to calculate outgoing power from nodes, as well as node voltage magnitudes and mismatches at the final nodes of both the main feeder and laterals. Based on these mismatches, the substation injection is adjusted appropriately, and the process is repeated until convergence is achieved.

KEYWORDS- *Distribution feeders, Injected powers, Load flow, Main feeder*

1. INTRODUCTION

Load flow is an important tool for satisfactory design and operation of distribution networks. At the design stage, load flow analysis is used to check whether the voltage profiles are expected to be within limits throughout the network. At the operation stage, it is run to explore different arrangements to maintain the required voltage profile and to minimize system losses. There are many solution techniques for load flow calculations. The solution procedures and formulations can be precise or approximate, with values adjusted or unadjusted, intended for either on-line or off-line application, and designed for either single-case or multiple-case applications. It is noted, however, that an acceptable load flow solution method should meet the following requirements according to Stott B.[1]:

- a) They should have high speed and low storage requirements, especially for real-time large system applications, as well as multiple case and interactive applications.
- b) They should be highly reliable, especially for ill-conditioned problems, outage studies, and real-time applications.
- c) They should attain accepted versatility and simplicity.

The conventional load flow methods, e.g., Newton-Raphson and Fast Decoupled, are very efficient and reliable for transmission networks, but for distribution networks they are not so efficient, and sometimes they may be unable to solve load flow. This is due to some inherent features of distribution networks, like radial or near-radial structure, high R/X ratios of lines, etc. Many researchers have suggested modified versions of the conventional load flow methods for solving ill-conditioned power networks. Kersting and Mendive [2] and Kersting [3] have presented a load flow technique based on the ladder network theory. Shirmohammadi et al. [4] have presented a compensation-based power flow method for weakly meshed distribution and transmission systems. Baran and Wu [5] and Chiang [6] have obtained the load flow solution in a distribution system by the iterative solution of three fundamental equations representing real power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude.

This paper uses basic algebraic equations from S.F.Mekhamer et al.,[7] and M. Baran et al.,[8] to solve the load flow problem in an iterative manner. Rather of employing the N-R approach and requiring the formulation of Jacobian matrices, the equations are employed in their simplified form. A straightforward concept based on the terminal conditions equations is used to construct system iterations and convergence. Reactive and active line loss equations are established. Phasor relations are

used to determine each node's voltage angle. Numerous feeders use this technique; one example is provided in the paper below. In comparison to current approaches, the process is incredibly quick and easy to comprehend and use.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION AND ALGORITHM

A balanced three-phase, radial distribution feeder with n branches in main feeder, $n+1$ nodes in main feeder, ℓ laterals and n_c shunt capacitors is assumed and can be represented by its equivalent single line diagram as in figure 1.

Figure 1. General model for a distribution feeder

The fundamental branch power flow equations are given as S.F.Mekhamer et al.[7],

$$P_{i+1} = P_i - \frac{r_i(P_i^2 + Q_i^2)}{V_i^2} - P_{Li+1} \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{i+1} = Q_i - \frac{x_i(P_i^2 + Q_i^2)}{V_i^2} - Q_{Li+1} + Q_{Ci+1} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{i+1}^2 = V_i^2 - 2(r_i P_i + x_i Q_i) + (r_i^2 + x_i^2) * \frac{(P_i^2 + Q_i^2)}{V_i^2} \quad (3)$$

Here we have

P_i, Q_i : real & reactive power flows at the sending end of branch i which connects node i and node $i+1$ respectively.

V_i : bus voltage magnitude at node i .

δ_i : bus voltage angle at node i .

r_i, x_i : resistance & reactance of branch i respectively.

Q_{Ci} : reactive power injection by the capacitor at node i .

P_{Li}, Q_{Li} : real & reactive power at node i .

Load Flow Solution Algorithm

The process of solving the load flow problem can be broken down into the following steps:

- i. Read the feeder data carefully.
- ii. Calculation of Power Demand: Determine the algebraic sum of active and reactive power demands for all nodes, including both the lateral nodes and the main feeder. Compute the total active and reactive load for the entire system.
- iii. Initial Power Estimation: Assume that the power supplied by the substation is equal to

- the total power demand, because losses are unknown at this stage.
- iv. Power Flow Calculation: Using the given equations, compute the real and reactive power flows at the start of each branch (e.g., branches 2, 3, 4, etc.). Determine the voltage magnitudes for each bus in sequence until reaching a junction (node) where a lateral begins. Since voltage magnitudes are independent of angle calculations during iteration, angles are determined only after convergence.
 - v. Power Distribution at Junctions: For the first iteration, distribute outgoing power from each junction node based on the connected load proportions. Calculate the power flowing to the next node in the main feeder and to the lateral at node. Use the load ratios to ensure consistency across iterations.
 - vi. Applying Load Flow Equations: Continue applying the power flow equations sequentially for the main feeder nodes, updating real and reactive power values and voltage magnitudes until reaching either another lateral or the last node of the main feeder.
 - vii. Convergence Check: If all real and reactive power mismatches at the last nodes of the main feeder and laterals are within a predefined tolerance (e.g., 0.001p.u), consider the load flow solution as converged. Then, compute bus voltage angles and finalize results. Otherwise, proceed to the next step.
 - viii. Updating Substation Injection: Adjust the substation power injections to account for calculated mismatches, using the updated power values.
 - ix. Re-calculate The Power Flow: Repeat step 4 by re-computing power flows and voltage magnitudes for each branch until reaching a node from which a lateral originates.
 - x. Iterative Corrections: In subsequent iterations, use previously calculated real and reactive power mismatches to adjust power values at bus . Then, distribute the outgoing power to the next bus in the main feeder and the corresponding lateral.
 - xi. Reapply Load Flow Equations: As in step 6, continue applying load flow equations until reaching the last node or another lateral. Power updates should be based on the most recent mismatch calculations.
 - xii. Final Convergence Check: If the solution meets the convergence criteria, compute bus voltage angles and display the results. Otherwise, proceed to the next correction step.
 - xiii. Final Substation Adjustment: Make final corrections to substation power injections based on previous iteration results and repeat from step 8 if necessary.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To check the validity of the proposed method it was implemented on many distribution feeder that have been also studied by other previous conventional methods. In this paper, we shows only one example which is implemented by the proposed method on a 12 bus distribution feeder as shown in Fig 2 . The line data and load are given in the table 1 and table 2. The solution of the load flow has been given in table 3.

Figure 2. Distribution feeder

Table 1. Line Data					Table 2. Load Data		
Branch No	Sending End	Receiving End	R (Ohms)	X (Ohms)	Node No	PL(Kw)	QL (KVAr)
1	1	2	1.093	0.455	1	0	0
2	2	3	1.184	0.494	2	60	60
3	3	4	2.095	0.873	3	40	30
4	4	5	3.188	1.329	4	55	55
5	5	6	1.093	0.455	5	30	30
6	6	7	1.002	0.417	6	20	15
7	7	8	4.403	1.215	7	55	55
8	8	9	5.642	1.597	8	45	45
9	9	10	2.89	0.818	9	40	40
10	10	11	1.514	0.428	10	35	30
11	11	12	1.238	0.351	11	40	30
					12	15	15

Table 3. Load Flow Solution

NODE NO	VOLTAGE MAGNITUDE	NODE NO	VOLTAGE MAGNITUDE
1	1.0000000	7	0.9637493
2	0.9943323	8	0.9553094
3	0.9890298	9	0.9472768
4	0.9805775	10	0.9444610
5	0.9698288	11	0.9435628
6	0.9665361	12	0.9433556

3.1 COMPARATIVE STUDY

For comparison purposes, we implemented the conventional load flow methods: Gauss-Seidel (GS), Coupled Newton- Raphson (NR), Fast Decoupled Load Flow (FDLF), and our proposed method. All simulations were conducted considering radial distribution characteristics. The comparative results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of comparison of load flow methods applied to the radial distribution system

Method	CPU time (s)	No. of Iterations	Max. Power Mismatch
Gauss-Seidel	0.77	55	8.05×10^{-8}
Coupled NR	0.61	3	3×10^{-12}
FDLF	Divergence	-	-
Proposed Method	0.05	4	2.3×10^{-8}

From the table, it is noted that the proposed method for load flow analysis in radial distribution networks is superior over other methods for its better convergence, simplified computation and faster execution. Also it is more scalable and reliable than other method.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a new approach to the load flow problem for radial distribution feeders that does not rely on traditional load flow techniques such as Gauss-Seidel, Newton-Raphson, and fast decoupling approaches. This technique iteratively determines the outgoing powers and voltage magnitudes of various nodes and mismatches at the final nodes of the main feeder and laterals using basic algebraic equations. The substation injection is then carefully adjusted based on the mismatches, and this process is repeated until convergence. Power is sent to the main feeder from a node where a lateral begins, and the lateral is adjusted based on the ratio of mismatches in the network's final nodes. Because of this, the approach is highly reliable and quantitatively effective for convergence for wide variation.

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